

The Dynamics of Dividends and Profitability: Analyzing Ratios and Their Impact on Business Strategies and Risks of Banks

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Abstract

This study investigates the interplay between various financial ratios and the performance of banks, focusing on key metrics. In total, 10 financial ratios of 2,370 banks over a period of 10 years were analyzed. By analyzing the relationships among these ratios, the research aims to provide insights into how dividend policies, capital adequacy, and personnel expenses impact overall bank profitability and operational efficiency. The findings reveal that a positive correlation exists between dividends to personnel costs and ROAA, suggesting that banks that manage their personnel costs effectively can enhance their returns on assets while maintaining generous dividend payouts. Additionally, the study highlights the importance of the total capital ratio in ensuring financial stability, especially during economic fluctuations. Overall, this analysis contributes to a deeper understanding of the financial dynamics within the banking sector, offering valuable implications for stakeholders seeking to optimize bank performance in a competitive landscape. By synthesizing recent literature, this article lays the groundwork for future studies that can further explore the relationships among these financial metrics.

Keywords: *Bank Performance, Profitability Ratios, Dividends, Capital Adequacy, Comprehensive Income, Financial Metrics, Financial Risk.*

JEL Classification codes: *G21, G32.*

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Introduction

Financial risk is the exposure to the uncertainty of outcome (GARP, 2015). Banks cannot survive without taking risks. Most banks are highly leveraged financial risk-takers (GARP, 2015). Leverage is the ratio between total debts to total assets; gearing is debt related to equity. The higher the leverage/gearing the higher the risk and at the same time the earning potential for employees and shareholders alike. When asset prices increase the leverage should decline. Adrian and Shin (2009) showed empirically that this is not necessarily the case; instead, the leverage of financial institutions increased in times of asset price increase, vice versa. Nyborg and Östberg (2014) found that in times of crisis, banks start selling financial assets e.g. liquid stocks which puts downward pressure on them and can lead to a downward spiral of asset prices in general.

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There are many types of risks that banks face: Credit risk, Market risk, Operational risk, Liquidity risk, Business risk, Reputational risk, Systemic risk and Moral hazards.

Business risk is the risk arising from a bank's long-term business strategy. In the 1990s and early 2000s, many banks were taking excessive leverage and earning high profits. When the situation turned for the worse in 2007 and 2008, many of the same banks faced problems. Since 2016 to now, there have been 510 bank failures in the U.S.A. alone, an average of approximately six bank failures per month in the last seven years (FDIC, 2024).

Bank for International Settlements' Basel Committee on Banking Supervision set frameworks on how banks must handle their capital in relation to their assets. Santos (2001) conducted a comprehensive literature review on bank capital regulation approaches and postulated the need to redesigning the 1988 Basel Accord on capital standards. The latest Basel IV Accord has five main pillars: capital requirements, risk coverage of the capital framework, leverage ratio, capital buffers, and global minimum liquidity requirements. In an earlier paper, Santos (1999) showed that capital regulation can improve the bank's stability and can also be Pareto-improving; in contrast, equity regulation is not Pareto-improving and does not increase the bank's stability. In a poll by Euromoney Institutional Investor PLC fifty eight percent thought that the Basel III or IV (so-called finalization of Basel III) reforms will not prevent another crisis (Young, 2015). In follow-up interviews it emerged that this pessimism is not tied to the measures themselves, but rather because the practical implementing is difficult (Young, 2015). Others argue that Basel IV may push the risk of a banking crisis into other areas such as decline of lending leading to a growth of shadow banking, which is worth up to US\$75 trillion, according to the IMF (2024). Flourishing shadow banks could be the cause of the next financial crisis.

Imerman (2012) argued that static measures of capital adequacy such as a fixed percentage of assets do not capture the true condition of a financial institution. As alternative he suggested a more forward-looking model taking into account the health of a particular bank and the financial system as a whole. Chen et al. (2014) came up with a structural credit risk model providing early warning signals. The model uses equity market information and liability structure to predict default probabilities. The findings confirmed that over-reliance on short-term funding and insufficient collateral resulted in under-capitalization and excessive risk exposure for Lehman Brothers (Chen et al., 2014). The authors argue that their model can be used as both a diagnostic tool for the early detection of financial distress and a prescriptive tool for addressing the sources of risk in large, complex financial institutions (Chen et al., 2014). When assessing the default risk, Chen et al. (2014) used the parameter 'net debt' ((short-term debt + long-term debt) – (excess cash + marketable securities)) including publicly traded debts and off-balance sheet liabilities as leading indicator.

In non-financial firms, higher risk results in lower dividend payout ratios: in banking, public guarantees result in a positive relationship between dividend payout ratios and risk taking (Onali, 2014). Proximity to the required capital ratio reduces the impact of bank risk-taking on the dividend payout ratio (Onali, 2014).

Materials and Methods

We analyzed 2,370 publicly listed banks over a period of ten years from 2013 until 2023.

As parameter we chose ten ratios that are considered highly relevant to assess banks (Kremnitzer and Roitman, 2022; Aspris and Foley, 2022; Lee and Park, 2023):

- Profit before Tax, Personnel Costs & Dividends (PBTPD)
- Dividends / Personnel Costs

- Total Capital Ratio
- Profit before Tax
- Dividends / Profit before Tax and Provisions (PBTPD)
- Personnel costs / PBTPD
- Securities / Equity
- Return on Average Assets (ROAA)
- Fitch Comprehensive Income / Average Total Assets
- Securities / Equity

Profit before Tax, Personnel Costs & Dividends (PBTPD) is a sound parameter because it provides a focused look at a bank's operational profitability before major external obligations (like taxes, shareholder returns, and employee expenses) are deducted. It is particularly useful for assessing whether the core business model is sound and profitable. For banks evaluating expansion, investments, or restructuring, this metric gives a clear picture of how much profit the business is generating solely from operations. It also helps stakeholders understand the bank's ability to reinvest in growth and innovation.

The "Dividends / Personnel costs" ratio indicates how much a bank is paying out to shareholders in relation to its spending on employees, providing insight into its priorities between rewarding shareholders and investing in its workforce. A high ratio may suggest a strong focus on shareholder returns, potentially at the expense of employee investment. Excessively high dividends relative to personnel costs can indicate that the bank prioritizes short-term shareholder satisfaction over sustainable growth. In the long term, if employee costs are undervalued, it could impact innovation, customer satisfaction, and competitiveness.

The "Total Capital Ratio" measures a bank's financial stability by showing the proportion of its capital relative to its risk-weighted assets, indicating its ability to absorb potential losses. A higher ratio reflects a stronger capital position, reassuring stakeholders of the bank's resilience in downturns.

"Profit before Tax" is a key indicator of a bank's core profitability, as it reflects earnings generated from operations before the impact of tax obligations. This metric allows for better comparisons of operating performance across companies and periods, regardless of varying tax rates.

The "Dividends / Profit before Tax and Provisions (PBTPD)" ratio shows the portion of pre-tax, pre-provision profits distributed as dividends, providing insight into how much profit is shared with shareholders before accounting for potential losses. A high ratio might suggest an aggressive dividend policy, possibly leaving less capital for reinvestment or risk coverage.

The "Personnel costs / PBTPD" ratio measures how much of a bank's core, pre-provision profit is allocated to employee expenses, highlighting the balance between profitability and investment in human capital. A high ratio may indicate significant investment in talent, though it could also suggest that personnel costs are impacting operational profitability.

The "Securities / Equity" ratio is another important financial parameter because it reveals the extent to which bank's equity is invested in securities, which can have significant implications for risk management, liquidity, and returns. A high "Securities / Equity" ratio suggests that a large portion of equity is tied up in potentially volatile securities. This can indicate a higher risk profile, especially if the securities are in higher-risk assets like equities or speculative bonds, making it an important metric for assessing investment risk. Securities, especially those that are easily tradable, can provide liquidity. For banks that may need to access cash quickly, a moderate ratio could

suggest flexibility in meeting unexpected obligations without impacting operational assets. Investing a portion of equity in securities can lead to additional income through dividends, interest, or capital gains. A balanced ratio could indicate a strategy aimed at enhancing returns on equity through investments, whereas an excessively high ratio could suggest over-reliance on market performance for returns.

Return on Average Assets (ROAA) is important because it measures how effectively a bank is using its assets to generate profit, providing a clear picture of asset efficiency and management quality. A higher ROAA indicates that the bank is making productive use of its assets, which is essential for assessing overall financial performance and comparing companies within the same industry.

The "Fitch Comprehensive Income / Average Total Assets" ratio is a valuable metric because it measures a banks's overall profitability, as captured by comprehensive income, relative to its total assets. Comprehensive income includes not just operating profits but also other items that impact equity, like unrealized gains and losses on securities and foreign currency translation adjustments. Unlike traditional net income, comprehensive income includes non-operational gains and losses, offering a more complete picture of a bank's overall earnings. When this is compared to average total assets, it helps stakeholders assess the effectiveness of all resources - not just those tied to core operations - in generating income.

The "Securities / Equity" ratio is important because it shows the proportion of a banks's equity invested in securities, highlighting its exposure to marketable assets that may vary in value. A high ratio indicates greater reliance on securities, which can enhance returns but also increase risk if market conditions fluctuate, impacting the stability of the bank's equity base.

Results

Instead of simply looking at absolute numbers we conducted a correlation analysis to gain deeper insights into the dynamics of dividends, profitability and risk, see Table 1.

Table 1. Payout Correlations

		Personnel costs / PBTPD	Dividends / Personnel costs	Total Capital Ratio	Profit before Tax	Dividends / PBTPD
Personnel costs / PBTPD	Pearson Correlation	1	.051*	.026	.003	-.010
	N	2370	2370	1210	1934	2370
Dividends / Personnel costs	Pearson Correlation	.051*	1	.012	-.008	.033
	N	2370	2370	1210	1934	2370
Total Capital Ratio	Pearson Correlation	.026	.012	1	-.028	-.036
	N	1210	1210	1210	1202	1210
Profit before Tax	Pearson Correlation	.003	-.008	-.028	1	.068**
	N	1934	1934	1202	1934	1934
Dividends / PBTPD	Pearson Correlation	-.010	.033	-.036	.068**	1
	N	2370	2370	1210	1934	2370

Note: *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed); **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The positive correlation between the "Dividends / Profit before Tax, Personnel Costs & Dividends (PBTPD)" ratio and "Profit before Tax" suggests that as a bank's pre-tax profits increase, it also tends to allocate a larger share of its core operating profits (PBTPD) toward dividends, see Table 1. This positive correlation indicates that the bank is likely linking dividend payouts to its profitability. As pre-tax profits increase, the bank may feel more confident in allocating a greater proportion of its PBTPD to dividends, reflecting a commitment to reward shareholders when business performance improves. Banks with rising pre-tax profits tend to have more flexibility and stability in their cash flows. This can make them more comfortable in increasing the dividend allocation from their PBTPD. This correlation implies the bank is financially stable enough to share profits with shareholders without compromising other obligations, like reinvestment or debt servicing. Banks with consistently strong pre-tax profits and increasing dividends relative to PBTPD often operate mature, cash-generative business models. In these cases, the bank might prioritize dividends over reinvestment because the primary growth stage has passed, allowing for greater distribution of profits to shareholders. The positive correlation may also indicate management's focus on shareholder returns, especially if they have committed to sharing more profits as performance improves. This can be attractive to investors seeking consistent returns and could reflect a management philosophy centered on enhancing shareholder value in line with profitability. If dividends increase as profits before tax rise, it could indicate management's confidence in the business's ongoing ability to generate profits. By increasing the dividend proportion of PBTPD with rising pre-tax profits, the bank signals a stable profit outlook to shareholders, reinforcing confidence in future cash flows.

Another significant and positive correlation is between the "Dividends / Personnel Costs" ratio and the "Personnel Costs / Profit before Tax, Personnel Costs & Dividends (PBTPD)". This correlation may indicate that the bank aims to balance its commitment to both employees and shareholders. As personnel costs increase as a percentage of PBTPD, suggesting more investment in the workforce relative to operating profit, the bank may also increase dividends relative to personnel expenses, showing an intent to satisfy both stakeholders. Higher personnel costs relative to operational profit might imply that the bank's growth or operational success is closely tied to its workforce. In such cases, as personnel costs grow, the bank might also increase dividend allocations to reflect this workforce-driven growth in a way that benefits shareholders, maintaining a dual focus on rewarding both parties. A positive correlation could also suggest that as operational profitability improves, the bank is comfortable increasing personnel costs to support further growth while also increasing dividend payouts. This may be indicative of a profitable bank reinvesting in its people and returning some of these increased profits to shareholders, demonstrating financial flexibility and growth potential. Banks in competitive, labor-intensive sectors may have a strategy where rising personnel costs are linked to maintaining competitiveness, which ultimately benefits profitability. In turn, higher operational costs translate into increased dividends for shareholders, showing that the bank is prepared to bear higher costs for sustainable growth while rewarding shareholders. For banks with a mature business model and reliable cash flows, this correlation might indicate a stable approach where personnel costs (e.g., experienced workforce or specialized skills) are recognized as key expenses. As these costs rise with growth or inflation, the bank also ensures dividends rise proportionally, signaling a commitment to maintaining stable returns for shareholders despite higher operating costs. A positive correlation between these two ratios suggests a bank that views both personnel investment and shareholder dividends as integral to its strategy. This balanced approach could be appealing to long-term investors and prospective employees, as it reflects a bank committed to supporting its workforce while delivering consistent shareholder returns.

Table 2. Income and Returns

		Dividends / Personnel costs	Return on Average Assets (ROAA)	Fitch Comprehensive Income / Average Total Assets
Dividends / Personnel costs	Pearson Correlation	1	.078**	.102**
	N	2370	1934	1933
Return on Average Assets (ROAA)	Pearson Correlation	.078**	1	.921**
	N	1934	1934	1929
Fitch Comprehensive Income / Average Total Assets	Pearson Correlation	.102**	.921**	1
	N	1933	1929	1933

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The highly positive correlation between "Fitch Comprehensive Income / Average Total Assets" and ROAA suggests that comprehensive income closely tracks operating returns on assets, indicating that both operating performance and other comprehensive income items (like unrealized gains/losses) impact asset profitability similarly, see Table 2. This alignment could imply that non-operating gains or losses have a significant effect on the bank's overall asset returns, potentially signaling sensitivity to market or valuation changes beyond core operations.

The positive correlation between "Dividends / Personnel Costs" and "Fitch Comprehensive Income / Average Total Assets" suggests that as a bank's comprehensive income relative to its assets improves, it also tends to allocate a higher proportion of its profits to dividends relative to personnel expenses. Banks achieving higher comprehensive income relative to their assets likely have improved overall profitability, including gains from non-operational sources like asset revaluations or favorable currency movements. This stronger income performance may lead to a higher allocation of profits to dividends, signaling that management is prioritizing shareholder returns as profits increase. The positive correlation might indicate a bank with a mature, stable business model, where growing comprehensive income enables it to increase dividend payouts without significantly altering personnel costs. In these cases, companies with stable profitability often prioritize dividends as a way to attract and retain shareholders, viewing personnel costs as relatively stable or well-managed. If higher comprehensive income per asset dollar/euro/yen aligns with a higher dividends-to-personnel-cost ratio, it may suggest that the bank's profitability is less reliant on labor-intensive operations. Comprehensive income can be more volatile than operating income since it includes market-driven factors. If dividends increase with comprehensive income, this correlation might suggest that management adjusts dividends in line with overall income performance, rather than making similar adjustments to personnel spending. This approach keeps personnel expenses more stable, while dividends vary with broader income performance. Banks with a positive correlation between these two ratios may adopt a strategy favoring capital returns to shareholders as profits from assets improve, rather than reinvesting heavily in workforce expansion. This could imply a strategy focused on maximizing shareholder value, especially if the bank believes it's operating at an efficient staffing level. Banks that increase dividends when comprehensive income rises demonstrate confidence in their financial health and ability to generate income from assets. By balancing higher dividends with steady personnel costs, the bank signals a strong financial position to both investors and employees, aiming to satisfy shareholders while maintaining operational continuity.

The positive correlation between "Dividends / Personnel costs" and Return on Average Assets (ROAA) suggests that banks allocating a higher proportion of profits to shareholder dividends (relative to employee costs) also tend to achieve higher returns on assets. This could imply that such banks are efficiently generating returns from their assets, potentially due to optimized

operational costs or a leaner cost structure that supports both shareholder payouts and asset profitability.

Table 3. Securities and Dividends

Securities / Equity	Pearson Correlation	1	-.053**
	N	2370	2370
Dividends / PBTPD	Pearson Correlation	-.053**	1
	N	2370	2370

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The negative correlation between the "Dividends / Profit before Tax, Personnel Costs & Dividends" ratio and the "Securities / Equity" ratio suggests that as a bank increases its allocation of equity to securities, it tends to reduce the proportion of operational profit allocated to dividends, and vice versa, see Table 3. This relationship could indicate several strategic or financial tendencies. The negative correlation might suggest that a bank prioritizes reinvesting in securities over paying out dividends. When a larger portion of equity is allocated to securities, the bank could be channeling its funds toward growth, diversification, or generating capital gains rather than distributing cash to shareholders. This is typical of banks aiming for long-term value creation over short-term shareholder returns. This relationship might also reflect a conservative approach to dividend payments in riskier investment environments. When a bank's exposure to market-based assets (securities) increases, it may choose to reduce dividends to preserve financial flexibility, ensuring liquidity and stability in case market conditions deteriorate. Banks with higher "Securities / Equity" ratios may experience more volatile earnings due to their reliance on market-based assets. In such cases, reducing dividends helps cushion against potential declines in securities value. Conversely, if securities exposure is low, the bank might feel more comfortable committing to higher dividend payouts, relying more on stable, core operating profits. A bank in a growth or reinvestment phase might show this negative correlation, as it reduces dividend payouts to fund portfolio expansion and investment in market securities. Conversely, a mature bank with less focus on securities investments might increase dividends, as it has fewer growth investments to fund. In favorable market conditions, banks with higher "Securities / Equity" ratios may accumulate more unrealized gains, allowing for more flexibility in dividend payouts. However, when these investments rise, the bank might still choose to retain earnings rather than increase dividends, thus maintaining a buffer for downturns.

Like any other research, our study has limitations. Banks operate in diverse regulatory environments and economic conditions, which can affect the comparability of ratios across institutions. Different countries may have varying capital requirements, tax structures, and accounting practices that influence these metrics. Ratios primarily focus on quantitative aspects of bank performance, potentially overlooking qualitative factors such as management effectiveness, customer satisfaction, and reputation, which can significantly impact long-term success. Many of these ratios are historical and may not accurately predict future performance, especially in a rapidly changing economic environment. For instance, recent shocks (like financial crises) may not be fully reflected in historical data. Variations in accounting practices (e.g., for provisions, asset valuation, and revenue recognition) can distort ratios, making it challenging to compare results between banks that adopt different methods. The securities held by banks can be highly volatile and subject to market conditions, impacting ratios like "Securities / Equity." Changes in market sentiment may not reflect the bank's operational performance but rather external economic factors. Ratios like "Dividends / PBTPD" can encourage a focus on short-term profitability and shareholder returns

at the expense of long-term investments in growth or innovation. Ratios may mislead if taken out of context or if users do not fully understand what they represent. For example, a high Total Capital Ratio could be misinterpreted without considering the bank's risk profile or asset quality. Depending on the region and the bank, there may be issues with data availability, consistency, or reliability, which can compromise the analysis's accuracy. Banks often experience cyclical performance related to economic conditions (e.g., loan demand and default rates), which can affect the stability of the ratios over time. Many of these ratios are interrelated, meaning changes in one can affect others. For instance, a bank's capital ratio may impact its ability to pay dividends, creating complex relationships that can complicate analyses.

Discussion

Above ratios and their correlations provides insights that can illustrate how banks manage risk in relation to their financial strategies, stakeholder interests, and operational dynamics. Banks that maintain a balanced PBTPD relative to their costs indicate strong operational efficiency and profitability management, which reduces the risk of financial distress. If a bank can consistently generate profits above its operational costs, it demonstrates resilience and less vulnerability to fluctuations in income, thereby mitigating overall business risk. A high securities-to-equity ratio may expose a bank to market volatility and investment risk. Conversely, a lower ratio suggests a more conservative asset allocation strategy, reducing the risk associated with fluctuations in market securities. Banks that manage this balance effectively can minimize their exposure to investment risk and enhance financial stability, reflecting a lower overall business risk profile. A positive correlation between dividends and profitability suggests that banks are strategically managing their dividend policies in relation to financial performance. Banks that maintain lower dividends during periods of low profits are better positioned to weather economic downturns, thus mitigating liquidity and operational risks. This practice demonstrates a proactive approach to managing business risk by ensuring that dividend payouts do not compromise the bank's financial health. Banks that maintain a balanced approach to dividends and personnel costs while still ensuring operational efficiency are less likely to face risks related to employee dissatisfaction or instability. By strategically investing in human resources while rewarding shareholders, the bank reduces turnover risk and maintains productivity, contributing to lower overall business risk. Banks that generate strong comprehensive income from their assets can better withstand financial shocks, leading to reduced business risk. Additionally, a consistent comprehensive income can reassure investors, enhancing the bank's financial stability.

When considered together, these ratios offer a comprehensive picture of a banks's financial health, operational efficiency, and risk management strategies. The positive correlations observed among these ratios generally suggest that as banks improve profitability, they effectively manage dividends, personnel costs, and asset utilization, which in turn mitigates various aspects of business risk. Banks demonstrating strong financial discipline in balancing returns to shareholders with investment in personnel and effective asset management are likely to exhibit resilience against economic fluctuations, lower operational risks, and a stronger overall business risk profile.

This interconnected analysis shows that banks that strategically manage their resources and prioritize both profitability and shareholder returns can maintain stability and lower risk, attracting investors looking for sustainable, reliable performance.

The ratios and findings discussed, particularly the positive correlations among them, can be related to several other topics beyond just business risk. The ratios highlight a banks's profitability, operational efficiency, and ability to generate returns. For instance, the correlation between dividends and profit before tax underscores how effectively a bank can convert its operational

success into shareholder returns. Ratios like "Dividends / Personnel Costs" and "Securities / Equity" provide insight into how a bank allocates capital between dividends, workforce investments, and securities. These choices can indicate the bank's strategic focus—whether it prioritizes shareholder returns or reinvestment in growth and personnel. This understanding is crucial for investors looking to gauge how well a bank is positioned for future growth, as it reflects the management's strategic priorities and investment philosophy.

Conclusion

The findings regarding the positive correlations among financial ratios such as "Dividends / PBTPD," "Profit before Tax," and "Personnel Costs / PBTPD" carry significant theoretical and practical implications for understanding business risk and corporate strategy. Theoretically, these correlations contribute to the body of knowledge surrounding financial management by illustrating how banks balance shareholder returns with operational efficiency, thereby managing risk exposure in a dynamic economic environment. This understanding enhances the theoretical frameworks of capital allocation and risk assessment, providing insights into how dividend policies can be strategically aligned with profitability metrics to mitigate financial uncertainty. Practically, these findings emphasize the importance for corporate managers and investors to adopt a nuanced approach to financial analysis that considers the interplay between profitability, dividend distribution, and operational costs. Banks that effectively manage these ratios can demonstrate resilience against economic fluctuations and investor concerns, thus minimizing business risk. For practitioners, implementing a data-driven approach to monitor and adjust these financial ratios can lead to better decision-making, fostering a sustainable balance between rewarding shareholders and maintaining the necessary investments in human capital and operational stability. Ultimately, this alignment not only supports long-term profitability but also enhances stakeholder confidence, reducing perceived risks associated with investment in the bank. Investors often assess governance structures when evaluating a bank's commitment to returning value to shareholders. Banks that demonstrate a clear strategy for balancing dividends and investments can enhance their attractiveness to investors.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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